

Understanding Information Needs on Permanent Contraception During Cesarean Section: A Cross-Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Permanent contraception during cesarean section is an effective and convenient method for postpartum family planning; however, women's information needs and influencing factors remain inadequately explored, particularly in low-resource settings like Bangladesh. Aim of the study: To assess the information needs and determinants regarding permanent contraception during cesarean section among women in Bangladesh. **Methods & Materials:** This cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at a tertiary care hospital in Bangladesh over a 6-month period. A total of 120 pregnant women undergoing cesarean section were selected using purposive sampling. Data were collected through face-to-face interviews using a structured questionnaire covering socio-demographic characteristics, obstetric history, awareness, information needs, and acceptance of permanent contraception. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 26. **Result:** Among participants, 41.67% were aged 26–30 years, and 51.67% resided in rural areas. Awareness of permanent contraception was 80%, but correct knowledge was lower (58.33%). The majority expressed the need for detailed counseling (78.33%), information on safety (75%), and partner involvement in decision-making (73.33%). The acceptance rate for permanent contraception during cesarean section was 51.67%. Acceptance was significantly associated with age >30 years ($p=0.003$), multiparity ($p=0.048$), completed family size ($p<0.001$), prior knowledge ($p=0.041$), counseling received ($p=0.001$), and partner involvement ($p=0.006$). **Conclusion:** Women undergoing cesarean section demonstrate significant unmet information needs regarding permanent contraception. Structured counseling, improved provider communication, and partner involvement are essential to

enhance informed decision-making and acceptance.

Keywords: Permanent contraception, cesarean section, information needs, family planning, Bangladesh, counseling

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INTRODUCTION

Permanent contraception is a highly effective method intended to permanently prevent pregnancy, most commonly performed by tubal ligation or salpingectomy, and is often chosen by women who have completed childbearing^[1,2]. In obstetric practice, cesarean section creates a valuable opportunity to complete the procedure during the same admission, improving convenience and access to postpartum family planning^[2]. Globally, caesarean section use has risen to about 21% of all births^[3]. In South and South-East Asia, the overall caesarean prevalence was 13%, rising to 19% among institutional births^[4]. In Bangladesh, 45% of live births in the two years preceding the 2022 BDHS were delivered by caesarean section, making this setting especially relevant for postpartum contraceptive counseling^[5]. The information needs surrounding permanent contraception during cesarean section are shaped by parity, completed family size, education, socioeconomic position, partner influence, and cultural expectations, but also by whether counseling is timely, clear, and unbiased^[6,7]. Women may receive incomplete antenatal counseling, misunderstand the permanence of the method, or fear future

regret, while provider preference, operating-room logistics, and policy or paperwork barriers can still prevent fulfillment even when the woman has clearly expressed her wish^[2,8,9]. In Bangladesh, physicians often dominate the process and that women may receive little detailed information, highlighting a broader problem of information asymmetry in obstetric care^[10-12]. The main manifestations of unmet information need are not physical symptoms but decisional conflict, uncertainty, delayed consent, and unfulfilled requests for the procedure^[6,13]. These problems become more visible when counseling is brief or nonshared, and when women are not fully informed about alternatives such as tubal ligation versus salpingectomy^[6,10,13]. The principal advantage of permanent contraception during cesarean section is that it is immediate, highly effective, and eliminates the need for another operation or another postpartum visit for contraception^[1,2]. Salpingectomy may also provide potential ovarian cancer risk reduction, and randomized evidence suggests it is feasible at cesarean delivery with similar short-term safety outcomes, although it may add operative time and is not always technically completed^[2,10]. The disadvantages are its

irreversibility, potential future regret especially among younger women and the risk that adhesions, consent issues, or institutional barriers will prevent completion^[8,9,11]. Despite increasing interest in postpartum permanent contraception, much of the evidence comes from high-income settings and focuses on access or fulfillment rather than women's exact information needs at the moment of cesarean delivery^[2,6,13]. Bangladesh-specific evidence remains limited, and the existing literature still does not clearly describe what women want to know, what they misunderstand, and which counseling elements matter most in rural or lower-resource settings^[5,12]. This gap makes a focused, patient-centered cross-sectional study necessary. This study aimed to assess the information needs and related determinants regarding permanent contraception during cesarean section among women in Bangladesh.

METHODS & MATERIALS

This cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at 250 Beded District Hospital and some Private Hospitals, Bagerhat, in Bangladesh over a period of one year, from July 2023 to June 2024. The study aimed to

assess the information needs regarding permanent contraception among women undergoing cesarean section.

A total of 120 pregnant women admitted for cesarean section were enrolled using a purposive sampling technique, forming a well-defined study population. Participants were selected based on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure the validity and reliability of the findings.

Inclusion Criteria

- Pregnant women undergoing elective or emergency cesarean section
- Age ≥18 years
- Willing to participate and provide informed consent

Exclusion Criteria

- Women with severe obstetric complications requiring immediate life-saving intervention
- Patients with known psychiatric illness or inability to communicate effectively

Data Collection

Data were collected using a structured and pre-tested questionnaire through face-to-face interviews. The questionnaire included sections on socio-demographic characteristics (age, residence, education, occupation), obstetric and reproductive history (parity, number of living children, previous cesarean section), and awareness regarding permanent contraception (tubal ligation).

Additionally, detailed information was gathered on participants’ knowledge, sources of information, and specific information needs related to permanent contraception during cesarean section, including safety, effectiveness, side effects, reversibility, and preferred timing of counseling. Data on acceptance or refusal of permanent contraception and associated reasons were also recorded. Furthermore, factors influencing acceptance—such as age, parity, family completion status, prior knowledge, counseling exposure, and partner involvement—were systematically assessed.

Outcome Measures

The primary outcome was the level of information needs regarding permanent contraception during cesarean section. Secondary outcomes included awareness, acceptance rate, and factors associated with acceptance of the procedure.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software (version 26). Continuous variables were expressed as mean ± standard deviation (SD), while categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages.

RESULT

Table I shows that among 120 participants, the largest age group was 26–30 years (41.67%), followed by ≤25 years (33.33%) and >30 years (25.00%). Slightly more participants were from rural areas (51.67%) than urban (48.33%). Most had secondary education (35.00%), while 18.33% had no formal education. The majority were housewives (70.00%), with smaller proportions in service (13.33%), business (8.33%), and other occupations (8.33%).

Table I
Socio-demographic Characteristics of the Study Population (n = 120).

Characteristics	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age group (years)		
≤25	40	33.33
26–30	50	41.67
>30	30	25.00
Residence		
Urban	58	48.33
Rural	62	51.67
Educational status		
No formal education	22	18.33
Primary	34	28.33
Secondary	42	35.00
Higher secondary & above	22	18.33
Occupation		
Housewife	84	70.00
Service	16	13.33
Business	10	8.33
Others	10	8.33

Multiparous women (2–3) constituted the largest group (48.33%), followed by primipara (26.67%) and grand multipara (25.00%). Most had two living children

(43.33%), while 31.67% had one and 25.00% had three or more. Family completion was reported by 58.33%. A history of one previous cesarean section was

most common (43.33%), followed by none (36.67%) and ≥2 (20.00%) Table II.

Table II
Obstetric and Reproductive Characteristics (*n* = 120).

Characteristics	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Parity		
Primipara	32	26.67
Multipara (2–3)	58	48.33
Grand multipara (≥4)	30	25.00
Number of living children		
1	38	31.67
2	52	43.33
≥3	30	25.00
Planned family completion		
Yes	70	58.33
No	50	41.67
Previous cesarean section		
None	44	36.67
1	52	43.33
≥2	24	20.00

Table III shows that most participants had heard about permanent contraception (80.00%), while 58.33% correctly knew the procedure (tubal ligation). Awareness of timing during cesarean section was 45.00%, benefits 51.67%, and risks 33.33%. The main sources of information were family/friends (28.33%), media (16.67%), and others (13.33%).

Table III
Awareness and Knowledge Regarding Permanent Contraception (*n* = 120).

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Heard about permanent contraception	96	80.00
Correct knowledge of procedure (tubal ligation)	70	58.33
Knowledge of timing (during CS possible)	54	45.00
Awareness of benefits	62	51.67
Awareness of risks/complications	40	33.33
Source of information		
Healthcare providers	50	41.67
Family/friends	34	28.33
Media	20	16.67
Others	16	13.33

Table IV indicates that the majority of participants wanted detailed counseling before cesarean section (78.33%) and information on procedure safety (75.00%). Information on side effects was needed by 71.67%, partner-involved decision-making by 73.33%, procedure effectiveness by 68.33%, counseling during antenatal visits by 66.67%, and information on reversibility by 60.00%.

Table IV
Information Needs Regarding Permanent Contraception During Cesarean Section (*n* = 120).

Information Needs	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Want detailed counseling before CS	94	78.33
Need information on procedure safety	90	75.00
Need information on effectiveness	82	68.33
Need information on side effects	86	71.67
Need information on reversibility	72	60.00
Prefer counseling during antenatal visits	80	66.67
Prefer decision-making with partner involvement	88	73.33

Table V shows that 51.67% of participants were willing to accept permanent contraception during cesarean section, while 48.33% were not. The main reasons for acceptance included completed family (36.67%), avoiding future pregnancy complications (26.67%), and economic reasons (20.00%). Refusal was mainly due to desire for more children (23.33%), fear of complications (15.00%), lack of information (10.00%), and religious/cultural concerns (8.33%).

Table V
Acceptance of Permanent Contraception During Cesarean Section (*n* = 120).

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Willing to accept during CS	62	51.67
Not willing	58	48.33
Reasons for acceptance		
Completed family	44	36.67
Avoid future pregnancy complications	32	26.67
Economic reasons	24	20.00
Reasons for refusal		
Desire for more children	28	23.33
Fear of complications	18	15.00
Lack of adequate information	12	10.00
Religious/cultural concerns	10	8.33

Table VI shows that acceptance of permanent contraception was higher among participants aged >30 years (35.48% vs. 13.79%, *p* = 0.003), multiparous women (77.42% vs. 62.07%, *p* = 0.048), those with completed family (74.19% vs. 41.38%, *p* < 0.001), prior knowledge (87.10% vs. 72.41%, *p* = 0.041), counseling received (80.65% vs. 51.72%, *p* = 0.001), and partner involvement (83.87% vs. 62.07%, *p* = 0.006).

Table VI
Factors Associated with Acceptance of Permanent Contraception (*n* = 120).

Characteristics	Accepted (n=62)		Not Accepted (n=58)		P value
	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	
Age >30 years	22	35.48	8	13.79	0.003
Multiparity (≥2)	48	77.42	36	62.07	0.048
Completed family	46	74.19	24	41.38	<0.001
Prior knowledge	54	87.10	42	72.41	0.041
Counseling received	50	80.65	30	51.72	0.001
Partner involvement	52	83.87	36	62.07	0.006

DISCUSSION

Permanent contraception, particularly in the setting of cesarean section, represents a critical reproductive health decision that requires comprehensive, timely, and patient-centered information to support informed choice [14]. This cross-sectional study explored women’s information needs and acceptance of permanent contraception during cesarean section (CS), highlighting important gaps between awareness, knowledge, and decision-making. In the present study, the majority of participants were aged 26–30 years (41.67%), with a slight predominance of rural residence (51.67%) and secondary-level education (35%), whereas study reported by Rahman et al., presented a lower average maternal age (around 24.6 years) with fewer years of schooling (mean 3.2), and further indicated that factors such as higher maternal age, obesity, and urban residence were more commonly associated with the study outcomes [15]. The high proportion of housewives (70%) is also consistent with previous findings, suggesting that reproductive health decisions are often influenced by family dynamics and socio-cultural context [16]. Regarding obstetric characteristics, nearly half of the participants were multiparous (48.33%), and 43.33% had two living children. Importantly, 58.33% reported completion of their desired family size. Comparable findings have been documented in earlier studies, where parity and family completion strongly influenced contraceptive decision-

making [17]. These findings reinforce that CS presents a strategic opportunity to offer permanent contraception, particularly among women who have achieved their reproductive goals. Although 80% of participants had heard about permanent contraception, only 58.33% had correct knowledge of tubal ligation, and less than half (45%) were aware that it could be performed during CS. Awareness of risks (33.33%) was notably low. These findings are consistent with studies by SALUFU et al. and Makhathini et al., which reported that while general awareness of sterilization is high, detailed procedural knowledge remains inadequate. This gap may contribute to misconceptions and hesitation toward acceptance [18,19]. Healthcare providers were the primary source of information (41.67%), followed by family and friends. This aligns with findings from studies in similar settings, where provider-based counseling plays a central role in shaping contraceptive awareness [20]. However, the relatively low contribution of media (16.67%) suggests underutilization of mass communication channels for disseminating reproductive health information [21]. A key finding of this study is the high demand for information. Most participants expressed the need for detailed counseling before CS (78.33%), with specific interest in safety (75%), side effects (71.67%), and effectiveness (68.33%). Additionally, 66.67% preferred counseling during antenatal visits, and 73.33% favored partner involvement in decision-making.

These findings are in agreement with previous research emphasizing that timely antenatal counseling significantly improves informed choice and uptake of postpartum contraception [22]. The strong preference for partner involvement also reflects sociocultural norms in Bangladesh and similar contexts, where reproductive decisions are often made jointly. The overall acceptance rate of permanent contraception during cesarean section in the present study was 51.67%, which is comparable to the findings reported by Upmanyu and Kanhere, and also aligns with reports from other developing countries, where similar acceptance levels (around 47%) have been documented [23]. The most common reason for acceptance was completion of family (36.67%), followed by prevention of future pregnancy-related complications and economic considerations. On the other hand, the desire for more children (23.33%) and fear of complications (15%) were the leading reasons for refusal. These findings are consistent with previous studies, where fertility intentions and fear of adverse outcomes were the primary determinants of non-acceptance [24]. Importantly, several factors were significantly associated with acceptance. Women aged >30 years were more likely to accept permanent contraception (*p*=0.003), consistent with findings by Apodaca et al., who reported increased acceptance with advancing maternal age [25]. Multiparity (*p*=0.048) and completed family size (*p*<0.001) were also significant predictors, reinforcing the role of

reproductive goals in decision-making. Furthermore, prior knowledge ($p=0.041$), receipt of counseling ($p=0.001$), and partner involvement ($p=0.006$) were strongly associated with acceptance. These findings corroborate earlier studies highlighting that informed counseling and spousal communication are key drivers of contraceptive uptake ^[26].

LIMITATIONS

This study has several limitations. Being a cross-sectional design, it limits the ability to establish causal relationships between information needs and acceptance of permanent contraception. The study was conducted in a single tertiary care center, which may limit generalizability to the broader population of Bangladesh. The use of purposive sampling may introduce selection bias. Additionally, data were based on self-reported responses, which may be subject to recall and social desirability bias. The relatively small sample size may also affect the robustness of the findings.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights that women undergoing cesarean section have substantial but unmet information needs regarding permanent contraception. Although more than half of the participants accepted the procedure, acceptance was strongly influenced by age, parity, completed family size, prior knowledge, counseling exposure, and partner involvement. The findings emphasize that informed, structured, and patient-centered counseling—preferably initiated during antenatal care—is essential to improve awareness and facilitate informed decision-making. Strengthening provider communication and involving partners in counseling sessions can significantly reduce misconceptions and decisional uncertainty. Addressing informational gaps and ensuring timely, clear, and comprehensive counseling may enhance acceptance of permanent contraception and improve postpartum family planning outcomes in similar resource-limited settings.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None declared

ETHICAL APPROVAL

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee.

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